

An Executable Ontology Framework for Integrating Risk Management into Requirements Architecture

Oleg Vasylovych Moroz

State University "Kyiv Aviation Institute": Kyiv City, UA

omoroz@kai.edu.ua

June 2025

Abstract

This paper presents an ontology-based framework for integrating risk management into software requirements engineering through an executable semantic architecture. The framework formalizes requirement and risk models as OWL/RDF classes and uses reified n-ary relations based on universal ontological predicates to connect them semantically. ArgonDigital-style visual requirements models are mapped to ontological entities, while ISO-compliant risk artifacts (e.g., risk registers, mitigation plans) are treated as first-class semantic objects. The approach enables multi-layer reasoning across goals, people, systems, and data models. Risk elements are not treated as annotations but as contextual semantic instances that can be queried, inferred, and propagated. The ontology supports rule-based reasoning through SWRL, enabling classification, propagation, and automated traceability. This foundation opens up promising directions for ontology learning, model transformation, and executable knowledge in requirements-centric systems engineering.

Keywords: Executable ontology, Requirements engineering, Risk management, Integrated requirements architecture, OWL/RDF, Semantic modeling, ISO risk models.

1 Introduction

The complexity and scale of modern software development projects is growing every year, and so are the risks, despite the rapid development of tools to support the software development life cycle and maintenance. Even a cursory analysis of publications on this topic reveals an imbalance between the problem and the approaches proposed to solve it. Researchers' attention is focused on individual stages of the risk management process, and the methods used are limited mainly to improving the risk management strategy through careful development of plans, compliance with recommendations and standards, etc. Meanwhile, the problem of systematically studying the impact of risks on software development remains relevant to this day.

Today, software development lacks a complete understanding of how to effectively prevent and eliminate risks in a project. That is why a significant part of research is devoted to risk modeling and forecasting, but this area involves the use of methods for analyzing and modeling multidimensional phenomena and processes under conditions of uncertainty, and therefore the accuracy of such models is significantly limited, as they lack either metrics for measuring the cost of risks or understanding the impact of risks on each other and their integrated impact on the project as a whole. In this regard, it is not surprising that more and more researchers and practitioners are paying attention to ontological modeling of risk management infrastructure, but such models are usually aimed at either developing a knowledge base for the risk management domain as a whole or at identifying and classifying risks. Meanwhile, a key point remains unaddressed - the relationship between project artifacts (goals, risks, people, systems, and data) and the domain model. But here we face an objective problem that is inherent in the entire field of knowledge management. We are talking about the contextualization of knowledge, i. e. the dependence of concept semantics on context. The presence of verbal and situational contexts allows us to describe different and even contradictory knowledge. Again, knowledge elements can be reused in different contexts, which allows you to synthesize different points of view in the overall context of the project. Concepts pertaining to software development risks are considered

to be context-dependent. This is due to the fact that some risks are rendered meaningless outside of a particular context, while others manifest themselves differently in different contexts.

In such a situation, it would be natural to start with a semantic analysis of the requirements architecture since requirements are the source of most of the risk factors. Unfortunately, there are currently no approaches and mechanisms for integrating risk management into requirements development. So, in this article, we will try to identify ways to solve the problem of integrating risk management models into requirements architecture, and let us start by clarifying the key aspects of the risk management problem.

It is an inevitable consequence of software development projects that they contain various risks with the potential to exert a negative effect on the success of these projects. A comprehensive risk management strategy, incorporating proper planning, effective communication, and risk mitigation techniques, can help to mitigate these risks. However, the situation is further complicated by the inherent uncertainty of software development projects, particularly those characterized by agility. A synopsis of recent publications reveals several aspects of the project risk management:

1. Impact of project goals on project risks.
2. Analysis of risk factors in the project.
3. Risk modeling and forecasting.
4. Integrated impact of risks on project implementation.
5. Interaction and links between risks.

1.1 Impact of project goals on project risks

The goals determine the risks. Some of them may be identified in the early stages of the project, while others may be identified during the project implementation or after the uncertainty in the initial requirements has been eliminated. The project objectives are crucial to the formation of risks, as risks can be viewed as potential threats to the achievement of these objectives. Project objectives shape project risks by defining the scope, timeline, budget, quality standards, and stakeholder expectations:

- **Project scope:**
The project objectives are closely related to the scope of the project. If project objectives are clearly defined and understood, it is easier to determine the scope of the project and associated risks. However, if the objectives are vague or poorly defined, it can lead to scope creep, which can increase the risk of project delays and budget overruns.
- **Timeline:**
Project objectives often include a deadline for completion. This timeline can create risks such as missing deadlines, resource limitations, and technical issues that may prevent the project from achieving its goals on time.
- **Budget:**
Project objectives may include budget constraints or targets. These budgetary constraints can create risks such as insufficient funding, unexpected costs, and the need to cut corners to stay within budget, which can jeopardize the quality of the final product.
- **Quality:**
The project objectives may also include quality standards or targets. These quality standards can create risks such as technical problems, design flaws, and lack of resources or expertise to achieve the desired level of quality.
- **Stakeholder expectations:**
Project objectives may include stakeholder expectations, such as customer requirements, investor expectations, or regulatory compliance. Meeting these expectations can create risks such as misunderstanding, miscommunication, or changing requirements, which can affect the scope, timeline, and budget of the project.

One of the main challenges in risk management for software development is that risk management approaches typically focus on limited goals related to schedule, cost, and quality, while assessing the integrated impact of risks [17]. This means that, in addition to the above, other goals should be considered, such as balancing the product life cycle and technical skills in the team, coordinating distributed teams, supporting critical business processes, compliance with standards, product maintenance, security and privacy, work organization policies and culture, etc. Limiting the goals under consideration can lead to an increase in potential project risk factors and therefore leads to the risk of unforeseen events and undesirable consequences.

1.2 Analysis of risk factors in the project

The primary task in risk management is to identify and display risk factors in software development project environments. One of the proofs of this is many existing works that propose certain approaches to risk classification. One of the most well-known is the taxonomy of operational risks developed by the Software Engineering Institute (SEI) of Carnegie Mellon University. The SEI taxonomy consists of three main classes [12]:

- Product development - considers the characteristics of the product itself, the mechanisms for requesting a product (or service), and the results of development.
- Development environment - considers aspects of selecting an operating environment and decides how to perform the development.
- Program constraints - external influences on the development process are identified, including the integrated impact of other risk factors.

Each of these classes is divided into component parts called elements. Each element, in turn, is associated with a set of attributes or characteristics, traits, qualities or properties that are used to describe the element. The SEI taxonomy is a de facto standard and is often used in research, which makes it possible to compare and generalize the results obtained. As a result of studies based on SEI, it has been proven that risk factors related to software requirements and lack of technical skills of personnel are the most recurring and influential types of risks [21], and that implementation activities at the software development stage are the activities with the highest potential risk, while among the life cycle phases, project management activities are the most potentially risky [11]. It should be noted that various criteria are used to determine risks, such as: performance criteria [8], criteria for prioritizing requirements [1], criteria for prioritizing user stories in agile projects [27] and others.

The results of such studies are usually based on the empirical data covering dozens or even hundreds of different risks that have been recorded in software development projects. Among this set of risks, the most common risk categories that occur in most projects are identified. These risk categories include the following:

1. Technical risks - related to the technology used in the project, for example: choosing the wrong technology stack, using outdated technologies, non-compliance with technical requirements, etc.
2. Project management risks - related to ensuring the effectiveness of the workflow, for example: lack of project planning, inadequate project monitoring, or lack of communication between team members and stakeholders.
3. Resource risks - related to the resources required for the project, for example: lack of qualified resources, their unavailability, inefficient team size and skill balance for the project, unplanned staff attrition, etc.
4. Requirements risks - related to project requirements, for example: unclear or changing requirements, incorrect or incomplete requirements.
5. Schedule risks - related to the project schedule, for example: delays in project completion, schedule deviations or missed milestones.
6. Budget risks - related to the project budget, for example: cost overruns, cost underruns, or unexpected costs.

7. Organizational culture risks - related to the culture of risk awareness or relevant company policies, for example, strategic risk or operational risk.
8. External risks - related to external factors that may affect the project, such as market changes, regulatory changes, or risks associated with suppliers (outsourcing).

Despite many studies on identifying risk factors, there is still no complete understanding of how these factors affect software development projects. Moreover, in addition to the most common risk factors, each project may also have specific risk factors. To identify such risk factors, you need to understand the project domain context, goals, local environment, and other related factors. It is also necessary to consider the impact of the risk management strategy on the emergence of specific risk factors in the project, which demonstrates the benefits of risk management and motivates development teams to continuously improve the risk management strategy and use of risk management software.

1.3 Risk modeling and forecasting

To significantly reduce the failure rate of software projects, you need to gain a good understanding of the causes of project risks and how they can affect project performance. A natural way to achieve this understanding is through modeling. To model risks and predict their impact on the project, the following methods and approaches are traditionally used [20]: fuzzy logic, Bayesian networks, neural networks, software agents, Monte Carlo method, simple and multiple linear regression, principal component analysis, and others. The accuracy of such methods and approaches is usually significantly limited and the main reason for their limited capabilities is that they lack, first, proven tools for measuring software project risk that consider the various aspects of risk considered important by project managers; and second, a theory to explain the relationship between risk measurement models and project performance [29].

As an alternative to traditional approaches to risk modeling and forecasting, search engine optimization techniques for making decisions and optimize project parameters, known as Search-Based Software Project Management (SBSPM), can be considered [14]. This approach uses search optimization algorithms such as genetic algorithms, metaheuristic methods, and others to find optimal solutions in the project parameter space. Instead of making decisions based on expert judgment, search engine optimization algorithms are used. SBSPM can include multiple objective functions to optimize different aspects of the project, such as cost, schedule, quality, etc. Multiple objective functions allow you to balance decisions in the form of trade-offs between different aspects of the project, such as cost, schedule, and quality [26].

1.4 Integrated impact of risks on project implementation

The impact of risks on a project can be either positive (favorable) or negative (undesirable), depending on the specific circumstances and context, for example:

- The risk of a lack of clear communication within the team increases misunderstandings and slower development speed, which can affect deadlines, budget, and resources (negative impact).
- The risk of the use of new technologies, which may be unstable or not meet the requirements, can lead to delays in the entire project, changes in deadlines, budget, resources, etc. (negative impact), however, if it turns out that the new technology works reliably and meets the requirements, the project may gain in competitiveness, providing benefits that were not foreseen at the planning stage (positive impact).
- The risk of the delay in the development of a key component due to technical difficulties can lead to a delay in the entire project, which can affect deadlines, budget, and resources and cause negative consequences for subsequent stages of the project (negative impact).
- The risk of the incorrect estimation of the project's labor intensity can lead to delays (negative impact), however, if the project develops faster than planned, it can mitigate the impact of delays in deliveries and technical issues (positive impact).

- The risk of the changes in requirements may result in some features being difficult to implement on time (negative impact), but it can also provide an opportunity to improve the quality of the product, which can offset the negative impact of delays (positive impact).

To minimize the negative impact of risks on project success, it is important to consider the cumulative impact of all types of risks on project delivery. This is important for the simple reason those different aspects of the project, such as cost, schedule, quality, stakeholder, and user satisfaction, need to be balanced. This can help to avoid focusing too much on one aspect, which can lead to an increase in other risks. For this purpose, the risk management strategy should consider the following well-known standard recommendations:

1. It is important to use different risk categories (technical, project management, resources, requirements, schedule, budget, external risks, etc.) to identify and categorize all risks that may affect the project.
2. To assess the likelihood and impact of each risk on the project, use a risk assessment matrix or similar tool to prioritize risks based on their severity.
3. To develop a risk mitigation plan for each identified risk, consider several potential strategies and assign responsibility for each strategy.
4. Monitor the project for new risks and update the risk management plan as necessary. Continuously evaluate the effectiveness of mitigation strategies and adjust them as necessary.
5. Communicate the risk management plan to all stakeholders to ensure that everyone is aware of the potential risks and mitigation strategies in place. Active involvement of all stakeholders is required to improve communication and perception of risk, making risk management more acceptable and increasing the effectiveness of corrective actions.

Following these guidelines will help to effectively manage risks and increase the chances of project success, but project success does not depend solely on the systematic and thorough application of strategies and recommendations (models, methods, standards, etc.) based on practical experience. In general, the problem of systematically researching the integrated impact of risks on software development is still pending. While various approaches such as KAOS [28] and i* [31] provide partial support for integrating risk into requirements engineering, there remains a lack of standardized, goal-specific mechanisms for systematically aligning risk management with requirements processes. This gap indicates a strong need to better understand and formalize integration strategies tailored to contextual goals and system-specific criteria [17]. This is confirmed by the analysis of research results in recent years, from which it's seen that the attention of researchers, which was mainly concerned with the integrated risk management process, is now focused on individual stages of the process [20]. In such a situation, goal-driven integrating risk management into requirements development could restore the status quo, providing the ability to assess the complex impact of risks and minimize their consequences.

Several established approaches exist for integrating risk considerations into software requirements modeling. Among others:

- **KAOS** (Goal-Oriented Risk Formalization) (Knowledge Acquisition in automated Specification)
The KAOS methodology enables formal modeling of system goals, obstacles, and constraints. Risks are represented as *obstacles* that may prevent the satisfaction of high-level goals. Through goal decomposition and obstacle analysis, KAOS supports traceable reasoning about mitigation strategies. This approach is well-suited for systems where formal correctness and goal satisfaction are paramount.
- **i*** (Social Modeling of Risk through Dependencies) ((i-star))
The i* framework focuses on the intentional and strategic relationships between system actors. Risks are modeled implicitly through vulnerable dependencies, such as when one actor relies on another to fulfill a service (e.g., SLA compliance). If the dependency fails, goal achievement may be compromised.

- **SAFe** (Scaled Agile Framework)

The SAFe framework focuses on scaling Agile [18]. Risks are considered in the context of planning, program, portfolio and team management (Program Increment Planning) and are classified as Resolved, Owned, Accepted or Mitigated (ROAM). Focused on management levels, this framework does not have explicit formal risk models integrated with requirements modeling as well as a semantic or goal-based tracing of risks to requirements.

- **ArgonDigital** (Risk Reduction via High-Quality Requirements Artifacts)

Unlike KAOS or i*, the ArgonDigital [?] approach does not explicitly model risks. Instead, it reduces risk by improving the clarity, completeness, and correctness of requirements through the use of visual models (e.g., process flows, business objective models) and structured templates. This practical engineering approach aims to mitigate risk by eliminating ambiguity, miscommunication, and poor prioritization. The ArgonDigital methodology is closely aligned with the framework detailed in the book *Visual Models for Software Requirements* by Beatty and Chen [9]. In fact, the book reflects the applied experience of the Seilevel team (now ArgonDigital) and presents a structured pedagogical perspective on the same set of techniques. Both approaches employ the same core artifacts — most notably the Business Objectives Model — as mechanisms to link high-level goals to measurable requirements. While ArgonDigital offers templates and enterprise practices for operational deployment, the book provides semantic depth, illustrative examples, and practical guidance for analysts learning to ”think visually.” Thus, Beatty & Chen serve as a foundational resource that formalizes the intent and structure behind ArgonDigital’s practical methodology.

By comparing these approaches, one can highlight the complementary nature of them. While KAOS and i* provide analytical rigor and can use formalized semantics (useful for risk analysis), ArgonDigital — alongside Beatty & Chen — emphasizes risk reduction through practical engineering discipline and visual thinking, and SAFe provides support for Agile scalable process management. Table 1 summarizes the comparison of the approaches.

Table 1: Comparison of Risk-Oriented Requirements Approaches.

Criterion	SAFe	KAOS	i*	ArgonDigital
Risk Representation	ROAM (Resolved, Owned, Accepted, Mitigated)	Explicit modeling via obstacles	Implicit via actor dependencies	Business impact and priority-based
Formalization Level	Informal, process-driven	High (goal logic, formal reasoning)	Semi-formal	Structured templates, semi-formal
Integration with Goals	Weak (through Epics and Themes)	Strong goal-obstacle-resolution traceability	Medium (goals and dependencies)	Strong linkage to business objectives
Traceability of Risks to Requirements	Limited	Full traceability (obstacles to goals to requirements)	Partial (via actor-goal links)	Explicit traceability to value and objectives
Architectural Impact Analysis	High-level (via Architectural Epics)	Strong (obstacle impact on functional/non-functional goals)	Medium (socio-technical dependencies)	Visual models of decision impact
Scalability to Enterprise Level	High (portfolio/program/teams)	Limited	Limited	Medium

To summarize:

- SAFe uses a practical and adaptive approach, but has limited formalization.
- KAOS is the most formal framework that allows analytical modeling of risks in the form of obstacles and mitigation mechanisms.
- i* focuses on sociotechnical aspects and considers risks as a consequence of unreliable or unbalanced dependencies.
- ArgonDigital uses a structured business approach, integrating risks into decision-making and requirement prioritization.

1.5 Interaction and links between risks

Different types of risks can affect both the project as a whole and each other. In general, the different types of software development risks are interrelated, and eliminating one type of risk can affect the others. It is important to keep in mind that the relationships between risks are usually dynamic and their nature may change during the project, so it is important to constantly perform risk tracing when managing a software development project. Effective risk management is not possible without understanding these interactions and using mechanisms and organizational measures to minimize the negative impact and maximize the positive impact of risks.

According to ISO 31000, risks are defined as the effect of uncertainty on objectives, and risk management must consider not only individual risks but also their interactions and compounded effects. These interactions often manifest as systemic dependencies, shared causes, conflicting control measures, or cascading failures. To effectively represent such inter-dependencies in an ontology, we propose the following semantic typology of risk-to-risk relationships, which aligns with ISO’s emphasis on risk context, interconnectedness, and systemic analysis:

1. Influence (Mutual Impact):

- *Synergistic effect*: Addressing one risk reduces the severity or likelihood of another.
Example: Mitigating unclear requirements can enhance planning quality, indirectly reducing scheduling and budget risks.
- *Antagonistic effect*: Mitigating one risk increases another due to resource or process trade-offs.
Example: Compressing the timeline to avoid deadline overrun may reduce test coverage, increasing defect-related risks.
- *Neutrality*: Two risks have no observable interaction.
Example: A geopolitical risk may be independent of technical debt in a software module.

2. Causal Dependence: One risk is a logical or temporal prerequisite for another.

Example: Poor requirements documentation may lead to design misunderstandings, which increase the probability of implementation errors — especially if no validation steps are in place.

3. Conditional Association (Modality):

- *Direct causality*: One risk explicitly triggers another.
Example: Developer turnover leads directly to knowledge loss and project delays.
- *Contingency*: The relationship is probabilistic and context-sensitive.
Example: Migrating to a new cloud platform might increase security risk only if the existing compliance framework is incompatible.

4. Resource Conflict: Multiple risks compete for shared mitigation resources, introducing systemic vulnerability.

Example: Limited QA staffing exacerbates both UI test delays and backend integration issues.

5. Mutual Reinforcement: Risks compound each other’s impact, increasing combined exposure.

Example: Use of unstable third-party APIs and lack of system redundancy both increase the risk of failure under load.

6. **Control Point Interference:** Risks affect shared decision nodes or milestones in the project timeline.
Example: Scope creep and delayed stakeholder feedback both jeopardize the requirements freeze milestone.
7. **Temporal Sequence:** A risk only becomes active if a sequence of other risks unfolds.
Example: Post-UAT client dissatisfaction arises only after flawed system testing and undetected misalignment in earlier stages.
8. **Decision Impact:** Risks interact indirectly by influencing project governance or strategic decisions.
Example: Regulatory compliance pressure and high technical debt may jointly delay architectural refactoring decisions, increasing uncertainty.

In line with ISO 31000's view that risk is dynamic, systemic, and embedded in context, we argue that modeling these relationships explicitly in an executable ontology adds semantic traceability and decision support value. Each relationship can be instantiated as a semantic link object with a specific ontological predicate (e.g., Causality, Modality, Aggregation), and annotated with attributes such as directionality, conditionality, and influence strength.

During early risk identification stages, such detailed relationships may be abstracted into a qualitative interaction matrix. However, in in-depth analysis and simulation stages, especially under uncertainty, these relationships become essential for anticipating risk propagation, conflict, and mitigation overlap.

1.6 Summary of the present condition of risk management

In summary, with regard to the present condition of risk management in the domain of software development, the following observations can be made:

1. Despite many studies on identifying risk factors, there is still no complete understanding of how these factors affect software development projects. In addition, in addition to the most common risk factors, each project may also have specific risk factors. To identify such risk factors, you need to understand the project domain context, goals, local environment, and other related factors. It is also necessary to consider the impact of the risk management strategy on the emergence of specific risk factors in the project, which demonstrates the benefits of risk management and motivates development teams to continuously improve the risk management strategy and use of risk management software.
2. To reduce the failure rate of software projects, you must first develop a better understanding of the causes of project risks and how they can affect project performance. There are various approaches to modeling risks and predicting their impact on a project, but the accuracy of such methods and approaches is usually significantly limited and the main reason is that they lack validated tools for measuring software project risk that take into account the various aspects of risk considered important by project managers; as well as theory to explain the relationships between risk measurement models and project performance.
3. Different types of software development risks are interrelated in that they can affect not only the project as a whole, but also each other. For example, technical risks can affect the project schedule and budget, as delays caused by technical problems can increase project cost and time, or project management risks can affect resource allocation and project schedule.
4. To minimize the negative impact of risks on project success, it is important to consider the cumulative impact of all types of risks on project performance. To do this, the risk management strategy should follow certain guidelines, but project success does not depend solely on the systematic and thorough application of strategies and recommendations (models, methods, standards, etc.) based on practical experience. The problem of systematic study of the impact of risks on software development and the relationships between them is still pending.

2 Background and Related Work

2.1 Fundamental Concepts and Definitions

2.1.1 Risk and risk factor

Under the ISO 31000 [15] standard, the definition of “risk” is no longer “chance or probability of loss” but “effect of uncertainty on objectives”, which causes the word “risk” to refer to positive consequences of uncertainty as well as negative ones. Thus, risk management involves not only avoiding or mitigating negative consequences, but also identifying and utilizing opportunities that can bring positive results. While the goal of managing risks with negative consequences is to minimize or eliminate negative consequences, the goal of managing risks with positive consequences (opportunities) is to maximize or use positive results that may arise as a result of the risks. Therefore, from now on, risk management will be understood as the prevention and reduction of negative consequences of problematic situations, and the term “opportunity management” will be used to identify and use opportunities to maximize positive results.

In the context of risk management, potential threats are traditionally referred to as “risk factor” and existing problems as “risk”. A risk factor is an element or condition that can contribute to a problem, i.e. circumstances, situations or characteristics that increase the likelihood of negative consequences. Risk factors are the root causes that can affect the occurrence of specific problems. Based on the identification of risk factors, risk prevention plans are developed. For example, the absence of a clear technical specification can lead to product non-compliance (due to unclear requirements).

Risk is commonly defined as the “effect of uncertainty on objectives,” according to ISO 31000. This definition emphasizes the relationship between uncertainty sources and their potential impact on achieving specific goals. A risk is typically characterized by a combination of *risk source*, *event*, *consequences*, and *likelihood* [15]. To reduce the negative effects of risks, risk prevention and response plans are developed. When assessing risks, it is important to first identify the risk factors that may affect the project and then assess the specific risks that these factors may cause in the context of the project.

2.1.2 Risk attributes

In the practice of risk management (in accordance with ISO 31000), typical risk attributes are follows:

- **Probability** - the likelihood that the risk will materialize. It is an assessment of how likely it is that a given risk will become a reality. Probability can be assessed qualitatively (e.g., low, medium, high) or quantitatively (e.g., 0 to 1 or as a percentage).
- **Impact/Severity** - the degree to which a risk will affect the project if it materializes. The impact can also be assessed qualitatively (e.g., minor, moderate, significant, critical) or quantitatively (in terms of financial loss, delays, productivity loss, etc.).
- **Detectability** - how easy it is to detect that a risk is being realized. This may include the existence of indicators or metrics that allow you to monitor the development of the risk.
- **Risk Priority Number (RPN)** - a numerical indicator used, for example, in Failure Mode and Effects Analysis method to assess and prioritize risks. Formula for calculating RPN:

$$RPN = SeverityProbabilityDetectability$$

where each of these factors is rated on a scale, usually from 1 to 10, where 1 is the lowest risk and 10 is the highest. Accordingly, the RPN value can vary from 1 (lowest risk) to 1000 (highest risk).

- **Risk Type** - the category to which the risk belongs. It can be technical risk, financial risk, organizational risk, security risk, regulatory risk, etc.
- **Risk Source** - the origin or cause (factor) of a risk. This can be an internal factor (e.g., lack of resources, insufficient team qualifications) or an external factor (e.g., changes in legislation, economic instability).

- **Duration of Impact** - the time period during which the risk may affect the project. This can be a short-term impact (a few days or weeks/sprints) or a long-term impact (several months/years).
- **Time Frame** - the time period from the start of the project to the end when the risk is expected to occur.
- **Detectability** - how easy it is to detect that a risk is being realized. This may include the existence of indicators or metrics that allow you to monitor the development of the risk.
- **Mitigation Strategy** - plans or measures that can be used to reduce the likelihood or impact of a risk. These can be preventive or reactive measures.
- **Key Risk Indicators (KRI)** - metrics used to monitor and evaluate the level of a risk factor in a project. They are created during the risk identification and assessment phase and are then used to continuously monitor and control risks in the project. If project managers, customers, and developers focus on the metrics, they can be an important tool that provides early detection of potential problems and thus allows for timely response. To define KRIs, it is necessary to select the metrics that best reflect the level of impact for each identified risk and determine the thresholds above which action must be taken. For example, for the risk factor “Deviation from the schedule”, the thresholds may be as follows:
 - Less than 5% deviation - normal condition.
 - From 5% to 10% deviation - increased attention.
 - More than 10% deviation - critical condition.
- **State of the related project issue(s)** - the occurrence of a risk leads to an undesirable state or deviation from the state of a project artifact (project issue) that is being implemented according to a certain requirement or even several related requirements. Determining the state of an artifact is usually done by injecting quality control into the state of the issue. Each state typically has specific quality control activities associated with it to ensure that the artifact meets the required standards before moving to the next state. Here is a typical set of states for an artifact in a project, with a focus on quality control:
 1. Backlog : The work item is identified and logged as a potential task or feature.
 2. Draft: The work item is in the early stages of definition and requirements gathering.
 3. Approved: The work item has been reviewed and approved for further development.
 4. In Design: The work item is being designed, including technical specifications and architectural considerations.
 5. Design Approved: The design of the work item has been reviewed and approved.
 6. Development (In Progress): The work item is being actively developed or built.
 7. Code Complete (Ready): The development of the work item is complete, and it is ready for integration and testing.
 8. In Testing: The work item is undergoing various levels of testing,
 9. Tested: The work item has successfully passed all tests.
 10. In User Acceptance Testing (UAT): The work item is being tested by end-users to ensure it meets their requirements and expectations.
 11. UAT Approved: The work item has been approved by end-users and stakeholders after UAT.
 12. In Deployment: The work item is being deployed to the production environment.
 13. Done: The work item is fully operational and being used in the production environment.

2.1.3 Risk models

As noted above, a key challenge in software development risk management is the limited understanding of how risk models can be integrated into requirements management. Before addressing this integration, we must first clarify what is meant by a “risk model”. In the context of software engineering, the term *risk model* lacks a universal definition and is often interpreted based on the perspective or methodological framework in use. This section presents a comparative overview of how risk models are understood in international standards, guides, and key frameworks relevant to software requirements engineering.

The term *risk model* is not defined explicitly by ISO 31000. Instead, it describes the risk management process, including phases like communication, scope/context setting, risk assessment, treatment, monitoring, and reporting. It mentions the various models and tools that you might use within each phase, such as risk registers, risk assessment matrices, risk appetite and tolerance frameworks, and so on, as shown in the Table 2.

Table 2: Risk Management Process Phases and Corresponding Risk Models (based on ISO 31000:2018).

Phase	Purpose	Risk Models
Communication and Consultation	To help relevant stakeholders understand the risk, the basis on which decisions are made, and the reasons why certain actions are necessary.	Risk Communication Plan
Scope, Context, and Criteria	To establish a risk management process that ensures effective risk assessment and appropriate risk handling; includes defining the scope and understanding the external and internal context.	Risk Assessment Matrix, Risk Assessment Criteria, Risk Appetite and Tolerance Framework, SWOT Matrix
Risk Assessment	To identify risks, analyze and evaluate them.	Risk Register, Risk Assessment Matrix, Prioritization Matrix, Comprehensive Risk Profile, Risk Mitigation Strategy, Risk Scenario Maps, Decision Trees with Monetary Cost Estimates
Risk Treatment	To select and implement options for resolving the risk; involves an iterative process.	Risk Treatment Plan, Risk Response Plan
Monitoring and Verification	To ensure and improve the quality and effectiveness of the process, implementation, and results; includes planning, collecting and analyzing information, recording results, and providing feedback.	Risk Monitoring Plan
Documentation and Reporting	To document the risk management process and report its results using appropriate mechanisms.	Risk Status Reports, Risk Ranking Report

However, ISO 31000 does not define the higher-level management models like Risk Treatment Plans, Risk Status Reports, or others. These models are part of the broader risk management framework/process, often customized or defined by organizations based on ISO 31000 guidance or best practices. Thus, they can be seen as a formal or semi-formal construct that provides answers to:

1. What are the uncertainties?
2. How likely are they?
3. What is their impact on project success?

Similarly, the term *risk model* is defined by such guidelines as PMBOK and NASA Risk Management Handbook:

- Risk model is a representation of how elements of uncertainty (events, probabilities, impacts, mitigations) interact to affect project objectives [25].
- Risk model is a structured (qualitative or quantitative) representation that integrates uncertainty sources and impacts to support decision-making [24].

Mentioned above goal-oriented frameworks propose different conceptualizations of risk models within the scope of software requirements and system development, namely:

- SAFe employs a pragmatic approach to risk management using the ROAM technique (Resolved, Owned, Accepted, Mitigated) during Program Increment (PI) Planning. While not formally defined as a “model,” risk classification and ownership serve as operational tools for decision-making.
- KAOS introduces a formal goal-oriented risk modeling approach, where *obstacles* are identified as potential blockers to goal satisfaction. These obstacles are refined and mitigated systematically, enabling traceability from risk sources to high-level goals and operational requirements.
- i* does not define risk models explicitly, but it supports the representation of *softgoals* (e.g., reliability, security) and actor *dependencies*, which can indicate vulnerabilities or potential risks in socio-technical systems.
- ArgonDigital’s approach is business-oriented, so risks are documented through structured attributes (e.g., Impact, Likelihood, Mitigation Strategy) within contextual requirement models. It emphasizes scenario analysis and business value alignment rather than formal risk modeling.

The approaches to risk modeling in the frameworks are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Comparison of Risk Modeling Approaches in Selected Frameworks.

Framework	Type of Risk Model	Formalization	Main Risk Elements
SAFe	Procedural (ROAM)	Low	Risk categorization, ownership, PI planning
KAOS	Logical/Formal	High	Obstacles, goal refinement, mitigation patterns
i*	Socio-technical	Medium	Dependencies, actor vulnerabilities, softgoals
ArgonDigital	Contextual/Business-driven	Medium	Risk attributes (impact, likelihood), business scenarios

2.1.4 Requirements models

In requirements engineering, a *requirements model* refers to a structured representation of stakeholder goals, system responsibilities, constraints, and their interrelations [28]. In different relevant frameworks, requirements models are formed with different levels of formalism, abstraction, and goal orientation. Below is a brief comparative overview, which is summarized in the Table 4.

KAOS

Requirements model is a formal and structured refinement of system goals, agents, responsibilities, and obstacles. Its main components are:

- Goals: desired system properties (e.g., “Ensure secure access”).
- Expectations: external preconditions (e.g., user behavior).

- Agents: actors that perform actions (people, software, devices).
- Operations: functional operations that implement the requirements.
- Obstacles: risks or barriers to achieving the goals.
- Domain properties: facts about the system environment.

i*

Requirements model is intentional and strategic relationships among actors, goals, tasks, resources, and softgoals. Its main components are:

- Actors: autonomous units (people, systems, organizations).
- Goals: achievable goals.
- Softgoals: non-functional goals (quality, safety, UX, etc.).
- Tasks: actions that realize goals.
- Resources: objects that are used.
- Dependencies: one actor depends on another (e.g., "User depends on System to authenticate").
- Two main diagrams: - Strategic Dependency (SD) - shows external dependencies. - Strategic Rationale (SR) - shows internal motivations, decomposition (goal→task→resource).

ArgonDigital

Requirements model is a structured visual or textual representation that helps clarify scope, behavior, and data of the system. There are four major classes of requirement models [9]: objectives, people, systems, and data. Each class includes constituent models, as well as the bounding model that is one all constituent models of the category depend on, and which bounds the corresponding space: objective, people, system, and data. For example, objectives models describe the business value of the system and help you prioritize features and requirements based on their value. They include following models:

- **Business Objectives Model (BOM)** [2]
BOM define the main goals of a project that are key to success. This model bounds the objective space in a whole and consists of four components: 1) business problem, 2) business objective, 3) product concept, and 4) high-level features that solve the business problem. In the context of risk management, this model helps to orient all management actions to maximize the achievement of goals and minimize the risks that may threaten them.
- **Objective Chain Model (OCM)** [5]
OCM allows you to structure goals at different levels, from general to specific. It starts first with the Business Objective at the top of the chain, eventually linking to Features. Between the Business Objectives and Features are Objective Factors and Objective Equations. This model helps identify the dependencies between goals and risks at each level of the hierarchy, which simplifies the management of these risks.
- **Key Performance Indicator Models (KPIMs)** [4]
KPIMs incorporate KPIs into a process flow to help add priority information around the requirements, which are connected to the process step the KPI references. Incorporating KPIs into the context of risk management allows you to detect changes in the state of requirements that may affect the achievement of KPIs in a timely manner and take appropriate measures.
- **Feature Tree Model (FTM)** [3]
FTM allows you to hierarchically structure the functions or requirements of a product. This hierarchy is rooted by the high-level features that appear in the BOM. Therefore, feature tree helps to identify the risks associated with the absence or failure to achieve certain features, as well as to develop strategies for managing these risks.

- **Requirements Mapping Matrix (RMM)** [6]

RMM helps ensure that all of the necessary requirements are being considered and created. It is similar to a traceability matrix, however, it has additional columns allowing more than two objects' relationships to be mapped.

Table 4: Comparison of the Approaches to Requirements Modeling.

Aspect	KAOS	i*	ArgonDigital
Core Concept	Goal refinement and obstacle modeling	Actor-goal dependencies and softgoals	Visual models for business requirements
Formality	High (temporal logic, formal refinement)	Medium (semi-formal graphs)	Low (informal visual modeling)
Goal Types	Goals, Requirements, Expectations	Goals, Tasks	Softgoals, Business Objectives, Features
Risk Representation	Obstacles, threat modeling	Softgoal trade-offs, dependency conflicts	Risk captured via visual models (e.g., filters, impact trees)
Actor Modeling	Agents with assigned responsibilities	Explicit actors with dependencies	Implicit or omitted
Traceability Support	Strong (goal-operation-agent)	Medium (goal-task-dependency)	Varies by model type
Tool Support	Objectiver, KAOS-Tool	OpenOME, RE-Tools	Visio, Lucidchart, proprietary
Standard Compliance	Can align with ISO via obstacle/risk analysis	Limited direct alignment	No formal alignment
Application Domain	Safety-critical, regulated domains	Early-phase design, socio-technical systems	Business analysis, Agile projects
Automatic validation/verification	Complete support	Not supported	Not supported

2.2 Conceptual Relationship Between Risk and Requirements

As noted above, there are several attempts to link risk analysis with requirements modeling. In KAOS, the Obstacle Analysis extension enables the identification of potential threats to goal satisfaction [28]. In i*, softgoals and intentional dependencies have been used to represent uncertainty and rationale behind design decisions [31]. Other approaches propose augmenting use case models or process models with annotated risk information.

However, most of these integrations are limited in scope. They either focus on static annotations, lack full traceability with risk processes, or fail to support executable semantics required for automation and monitoring. Moreover, they often do not comply with ISO-standardized definitions or lack formal alignment with standard risk management workflows.

Since this is a baseline of the problem of integrating risks into requirements architecture, let's take a closer look at how it is implemented in the frameworks — high-formal KAOS and non-formal ArgonDigital.

KAOS

In KAOS, risk is not just an external consideration — it's formally integrated into the requirements modeling process through the concept of *obstacles*. Obstacles represent a core conceptual bridge between *requirements* and *risk*. An *obstacle* is formally defined as a condition or event that violates a goal. Obstacles can represent:

- Hardware/software failures.
- Human errors.
- Environmental disruptions.
- Malicious threats.

This makes obstacles a semantic equivalent to risks in the ISO 31000 sense: they threaten the achievement of objectives (goals).

KAOS links risks and requirements through several steps:

- Systematic identification of obstacles to each goal through:
 - Backward reasoning: what could prevent this goal from being satisfied?
 - Domain modeling: using operational domain knowledge to foresee exceptions or failures.

This step corresponds to risk identification in the risk management process.

- Once obstacles are identified, they can be:
 - Refined into more specific sub-obstacles (like root causes).
 - Quantified (e.g. through likelihood, severity, or confidence metrics).

This is analogous to risk analysis and evaluation phases in ISO 31000.

- For every significant obstacle, KAOS introduces resolution goals, which are new goals or requirements that either prevent the obstacle or reduce its impact. For examples, error detection goals, redundancy, user training requirements. This directly corresponds to risk treatment in ISO 31000.
- Tracing back each requirement to the goal and each obstacle to its failure. Thus, resolutions goals that address obstacles are traceable as risk-driven requirements.

Figure 1 illustrates an example of the Goal-Obstacle Model. It models goals, obstacles that can prevent the achievement of these goals, and mitigation actions that help overcome these obstacles. Here, risks are represented as obstacles to the achievement of goals.

Figure 1: Example of the Goal-Obstacle Model in KAOS framework.

ArgonDigital

While not as formal as KAOS, ArgonDigital integrates risk thinking into requirements elicitation and prioritization through models and best practices that balance business value, complexity, and uncertainty. It does not define a strict formalization of risk, but it incorporates risk analysis conceptually and operationally through its modeling techniques and prioritization schemes. Here's how it works:

- ArgonDigital begins by identifying measurable business objectives. Business Objectives Model is used to align goals and exposes risks. Each requirement is traced back to a business objective. If a requirement or feature cannot be traced to a measurable objective, it may pose a risk of delivering no value or even negative impact. This goal alignment helps identify:
 - gaps (risk of unmet objectives),
 - misalignments (risk of misinterpreted goals),
 - over-promises (risk of unrealistic objectives).
- Objective Chains and Feature Trees are used to trace impact of risk:
 - Objective Chain maps business goals → stakeholder goals → product features.
 - Feature Tree decomposes high-level product features into subfeatures and requirements.

If a requirement or feature has no clear chain of value, it may introduce scope risk, waste, or failure to meet expectations.
- Assumptions and Constraints Cataloging are used to identify risky dependencies:
 - Assumptions about technology, users, or data are made explicit.

- Constraints (legal, regulatory, performance) are captured as formal inputs to requirements.

If assumptions are not validated or constraints are misrepresented, they become sources of risk.

- Prioritization Models (Value vs. Complexity) are used to quantify risk in delivery. To achieve this, ArgonDigital uses structured methods such as: MoSCoW, Relative Ranking (based on business value), and Complexity-vs-Value matrix. High-complexity/low-value items are riskier, and prioritization models help avoid delivering high-risk, low-benefit features.
- Use Cases, Visual Models, and Prototypes are used to reduce misunderstanding risk:
 - Models like Process Flows, Use Case Diagrams, and Mockups reduce ambiguity.
 - Early modeling and prototyping reduce downstream rework risk.

Misunderstandings in requirements are a major source of project risk.

- Requirements Quality Criteria are used to prevent risk from poor specification. These criteria are written with a focus on: unambiguous language, testability, traceability, single responsibility. Poorly written requirements are a top cause of project risk (delays, defects, user dissatisfaction).

An example of the Feature Tree Model is shown in Figure 2 . This is a model specific to the ArgonDigital framework. It shows a hierarchy of features where risks can be linked to specific requirements or sub-functions. This helps to identify and prioritize risky elements during the requirements analysis.

Figure 2: Example of the Feature Tree Model in ArgonDigital framework.

2.3 Risk Management Process and Requirements Engineering Integration

It is crucial that the requirements and risk modeling framework align with standard risk management workflows. In this section, we will therefore provide an overview of how well the KAOS, ArgonDigital and i* frameworks meet the ISO 31000 risk management standard. We'll examine each against the ISO 31000's components of a cyclical process for risk management, which are:

- Communication and consultation
- Establishing the context of risk management
- Risk assessment
- Risk treatment
- Monitoring and review
- Recording and reporting

2.3.1 Communication and Consultation

Effective risk management requires a shared understanding among stakeholders. Requirements models, especially those grounded in formal ontologies, can serve as a semantic interface for consistent terminology and rationale exchange across teams.

KAOS

Early in KAOS, analysts gather stakeholder goals via agent and goal models. Building the goal–obstacle model is itself a communication tool: stakeholders see their goals, assumptions and obstacles visualized, which facilitates mutual understanding and consent. For example, obstacles (negative goals) are identified collaboratively as potential risks to goals. In practice, KAOS workshops and models ensure all views are captured – effectively implementing ISO’s call to bring diverse expertise together and share risk information. The goal graphs and related KAOS artifacts (agent model, domain model) become the shared language for consultation, making the basis for decisions and risk clear to everyone.

i*

The i* framework inherently captures stakeholder intentions and dependencies, making it a natural fit for consultation. At the Strategic Dependency (SD) level, analysts identify all actors (internal and external) and model who depends on whom for goals, tasks, or resources. At the Strategic Rationale (SR) level, each actor’s goals and tasks are elaborated. Creating these models requires iterative discussion with stakeholders, so i* modeling sessions function as stakeholder interviews. By bringing actors and their goals into a common diagram, i* makes it explicit which goals depend on which actors, fostering shared understanding of needs and concerns. This practice satisfies ISO’s goal of involving both internal and external parties in risk discussions. Moreover, i* can incorporate stakeholders’ perceived uncertainties: in the model, each dependency or softgoal can be discussed for its trustworthiness, thus treating the modeling session itself as a risk-focused consultation.

ArgonDigital

ArgonDigital centers on aligning stakeholders around business objectives and value from day one. The team works with both business and IT stakeholders to define a Business Objective Model – a prioritized list of project goals tied to financial metrics – providing a framework for scope and risks. This shared model of objectives ensures clear communication of what the project must achieve. Argon also uses visual models (e.g. objective chains, process maps) so nontechnical and technical people “all see the same pictures,” which boosts understanding of potential issues.

In addition, Argon’s process includes weekly status reports to stakeholders that explicitly show risks, issue health, and progress against objectives. By regularly reporting risk exposures and requirement stability, ArgonDigital implements ISO’s idea of timely two-way communication and feedback – for example, showing how scope or feature changes affect risk. In summary, ArgonDigital’s stakeholder-focused models and metrics (aligned with ISO’s objectives sharing) keep everyone informed and engaged on risk matters.

2.3.2 Establishing the Context of Risk Management

The definition of internal and external context, including objectives, constraints, and environment assumptions, is closely related to early-stage requirements modeling, as well as a basis for the steps of risk assessments followed by risk treatment. By establishing the context of risk management, the organization articulates its objectives, defines the external and internal parameters to be taken into account when managing risk, and sets the scope and risk criteria for the remaining process. The main goals of establishing the context are following:

1. Analysis of project goals to identify potential risks.
2. Analysis of the project process for redundancy and inconsistency.
3. Defining the boundaries of the risk management process.
4. Determining the criteria for risk assessment.
5. Selection of methods and tools for risk assessment.

KAOS

KAOS explicitly models the system context through domain and environment assumptions. The domain model captures real-world entities and invariants; the agent model delineates stakeholders' scope. These models define internal context (stakeholder roles, system boundaries) and external context (environment properties, constraints). By formalizing environmental assumptions, KAOS makes clear what conditions or laws the system depends on – exactly the kind of context information ISO 31000 recommends collecting. For example, an obstacle in KAOS (e.g., “network unavailable”) captures a contextual risk factor that can affect multiple targets.

In ISO terminology, KAOS provides documentation and communication of the “external and internal context” (mission, values, external factors). The goal graph thus embodies context: it shows how top-level goals refine into subgoals and assumptions. Each element of the model has its own origin, so the rationale for the goal is clear in its context. This provides a foundation for later risk steps: if the context changes, the impact on goals is traceable.

i*

In i*, establishing context is explicit. There are two main models in the i* framework: Strategic Dependency (SD) model and Strategic Rationale (SR) model. The SD model shows who the actors are and what they want, placing the system in an organizational network. The SR model then ties each goal to operational and business environmental factors. For example, an actor's goal might depend on a market assumption or a regulatory constraint, capturing external context as softgoals or belief dependencies. This modeling aligns with ISO's direction to share mission, values, and external factors (cultural, regulatory, etc.) among stakeholders. Because i*'s focus is on “why” a system is needed, it forces analysts to articulate the wider context of each goal.

Thus, the i*'s models show what environmental assumptions or stakeholder objectives underlie each requirement. By linking requirements back to this context (through dependency chains), i* ensures risks are considered in the frame of business and operational environment.

ArgonDigital

ArgonDigital starts by defining the business context. Its business goal model links the project to organizational strategy and metrics. It takes into account the internal context (company goals and success criteria) and even the external context (market and regulatory factors) through the selected objectives. Next, Argon's goal chain analysis determines the monetary value of functions by embedding economic context into the decision-making process. By quantifying the contribution of each element to the objectives, ArgonDigital effectively establishes the risk context: low-value elements are contextual “noise” that needs to be cut out, while high-value elements attract attention. This satisfies ISO's need to define scope and criteria by linking requirements to the organizational context.

ArgonDigital also uses visual models of people and systems that depend on goal models to represent stakeholders and interfaces. In short, ArgonDigital’s context definition activities (goals, values, stakeholder personas) clearly align requirements with the enterprise environment so that risk is assessed against the right criteria.

2.3.3 Risk Assessment

In addition to ISO 31000, ISO/IEC 31010 [16] provides information on the selection and application of risk assessment steps and methods. ISO/IEC 31010 provides a list of risk assessment methods, but the choice of specific methods is entirely dependent on the circumstances, and their results depend largely on how well they take into account the different aspects of risk that affect the metrics of the different stakeholders, as well as their ability to measure progress toward goals. Each method has its own advantages and limitations, and often the best results are achieved by combining several methods to provide a more complete and accurate risk analysis. Moreover, some of them have been found to have limited validity when used in isolation, others can be used, in addition to risk assessment, at other stages of the risk management process [19].

Thus, this includes risk identification, analysis, and evaluation of the consequences. Integration with requirements models can facilitate:

- Mapping obstacles to risks,
- Linking risk attributes to goal vulnerabilities,
- Reasoning over propagation of risks across goal dependencies.

KAOS

KAOS integrates risk assessment into its goal/obstacle analysis. Each obstacle is naturally a risk source that is a condition hindering a goal. In practice, KAOS models can be annotated with risk metrics. Boness et al.’s method [10] is illustrative: they attach four risk factors (like likelihood of error and knowledge gaps) to each goal and compute composite Feasibility and Adequacy scores. They treat obstacles as “surrogate root goals” for risk measurement, so unresolved obstacles flag high risk. This yields a risk profile over the goal graph. For example, a crucial goal with many high-risk leaf goals (poor feasibility) will be flagged as risky. The proportional value/cost (PValue/PCost) of each goal are also used, so that high-value goals with high risk get attention.

In summary, KAOS risk assessment means systematically walking the goal–obstacle graph: identify all obstacles (risk candidates), estimate their likelihood/impact via expert judgment, and propagate those values up the goal tree. The formal KAOS reasoning then highlights which goals (and hence requirements) are most at risk.

i*

In i*, risk is modeled through the dependencies. A key concept is dependency vulnerability: an “open” dependency implies low impact, whereas a “critical” dependency implies high impact. For example, if actor A critically depends on actor B for a key resource, and B’s reliability is doubtful, that is a high-risk scenario. Giannoulis et al. [13] suggest mapping these categories to impact levels, and assigning likelihoods to form a risk matrix. The analyst identifies risks by examining each strategic dependency in the SD/SR models: “what can go wrong?” at each link or goal. They then assess impact (via the dependency classification) and likelihood (via stakeholder input or historical data). If needed, threats or negative goals can be added to the SR model, and their effect traced to stakeholder goals. The result is a prioritized list of dependencies/goals with risk scores, analogous to ISO’s risk register but embedded in the i* models.

ArgonDigital

ArgonDigital does not define a proprietary risk model, but its artifacts support risk detection. Each requirement or feature can carry a risk attribute (Risk as an Attribute) based on factors like

ambiguity, complexity, volatility, etc. These attributes feed into project risk discussions. Additionally, Argon’s experts recommend value analysis: features are scored by business value, so a high-cost feature with uncertain requirements becomes a high-risk item. Combining risk with business value in a matrix surfaces “Key Driving Requirements” that have both high value and high risk [30], and, in fact, is equivalent to using the ISO’s Risk Assessment Matrix or Prioritization Matrix.

In practice, teams would review the Business Objectives and Feature lists with stakeholders to identify which items carry the biggest exposure. The visual models also aid assessment: for example, if a needed actor or interface isn’t shown in the model, that gap is a latent risk. Thus ArgonDigital assesses risk by examining each feature/requirement in the context of business value and known instability, using simple matrices or dashboards to rank them.

2.3.4 Risk Treatment

Requirements representing a goal model can be systematically traced to specific risk mitigation strategies, such as avoiding the risk, taking or increasing the risk, and others. This allows for structured evaluation of countermeasure design options based on risk exposure and effectiveness.

KAOS

In KAOS, treating risk means refining the goal model to eliminate obstacles. This typically involves adding new goals or constraints that counteract each obstacle. For example, if “unauthorized access” is an obstacle to a security goal, the modeler would introduce a sub-goal like “authenticate users” and decompose accordingly. It looks like for each threat one derives a preventative goal. The updated KAOS model thus encodes the mitigation strategy. All paths that led to an obstacle are now broken by new subgoals or stricter invariants. In ISO terms, this is risk treatment: we have chosen to mitigate by redesign. The artifact is the refined model: showing that, for instance, an originally critical obstacle is now addressed by design changes. Trace links in KAOS ensure that each new treatment goal can be traced to the original risk source.

i*

In i*, risk treatment means revising the intentional model to shore up vulnerabilities. Using the earlier analysis, the team alters the i* diagram by adding tasks, dependencies or actors to cover weak spots. For instance, Giannoulis et al. [13] describe adding a new “Good Online Service” softgoal dependency to reduce the risk from an unreliable hosting provider. More generally, one might change a dependency from “open” to “committed” (by negotiating a formal agreement), or add an extra provider to remove a single point of failure. The updated SR/SD models then guide requirement changes: new tasks or quality goals translate into specific requirements. Thus, I* treatment is encoded in the model itself. This is done, for example, by new decomposition. Thus, the final i* model and rationale capture the chosen mitigation strategy.

ArgonDigital

ArgonDigital’s risk treatment is very practical: cut scope and re-prioritize. Features identified as low-value or high-risk are removed or deferred. ArgonDigital explicitly notes that “65% of features are rarely or never used,” and their approach is to cut such features early. This directly eliminates the risk of wasted effort. For remaining features, ArgonDigital focuses on high-value ones first (their cost-value analysis drives prioritization). When a high-risk requirement is found (e.g. ambiguous interface), it becomes the focus of early elaboration. In risk treatment strategy they also relies on constant stakeholder feedback: the weekly review mentions “risks” and “issue resolution” so that if a requirement problem emerges it’s immediately discussed and fixed. For example, an unclear requirement logged in the issue tracker is treated (clarified) before coding proceeds. In effect, ArgonDigital’s treatment options include scope reduction (avoiding risky features) and issue management (correcting risky requirements), mirroring ISO’s treatment options of avoidance and mitigation.

2.3.5 Monitoring and Review

This stage of the ISO 31000 risk management process ensures that risk treatments — many of which are embedded as requirement — are effective, relevant, and continuously aligned with system goals and stakeholder needs. It is crucial because:

- Closes the loop between identified risks and actual requirement performance.
- Detects unintended consequences or gaps in treatment-related requirements.
- Enables realignment of requirements with changing risk exposure.
- Facilitates continuous improvement of both risk and requirements processes.

KAOS

KAOS's formal models enable ongoing review. As development proceeds, the goal graphs and obstacle lists are revisited: Are any obstacles still unresolved? Have underlying assumptions changed? For example, if an interface specification changes, one can traverse the trace links in the model to see which goals are affected and re-assess their risk. Though KAOS doesn't define a separate "monitoring" artifact, one practical approach is to treat unresolved obstacles as tracked risks. Periodically, the team can recalculate feasibility scores (like Boness et al. did) to see if risk levels have shifted. The KAOS database (tools like Objectiver) can produce reports on which requirements/goals have changed, acting as a log of progress. In essence, maintaining and updating the KAOS model enacts the ISO stage of monitoring: it keeps risk information current in the model structure itself.

i*

In an i* approach, monitoring means revisiting the models as things change. If an actor's reliability or a dependency's availability changes, the model is updated and risk reassessed. Because the SR model records rationale, it is relatively easy to check whether a mitigation has been fully implemented. For instance, the risk is resolved if the aforementioned 'Good Online Service' soft goal has corresponding tasks in later specifications. Also, one can supplement i* with a simple risk tracking sheet: each critical dependency identified in the model can be listed with its status (e.g. "mitigation deployed").

If tool support is used, version differences in the i* model serve as a change log. Conceptually, i* allows continuous review by virtue of its integrated stakeholder view – changing any assumption (e.g. business context) forces a reexamination of the affected goals and associated risks. This loosely follows ISO's cycle: i* models and their derived requirements act as the evolving documentation that is checked at each review.

ArgonDigital

Monitoring is essential built into ArgonDigital's process. Each week the team sends a report to stakeholders that includes current risks and metrics (e.g. scope changes, issue burn-down, requirements coverage). For example, the "health of requirements" metric reports how complete and traced the requirements are – a drop in health is a risk warning. The issue tracker serves as a continuous indicator: if issues (questions, defects) aren't closing, it signals growing risk. These leading indicators, such as issue trends and interface definition progress, are precisely recommended by ArgonDigital as predictive signals. In practice, ArgonDigital teams will respond if say the issue resolution rate plateaus: that triggers a stakeholder meeting (like ISO's "review progress"). The visual models and requirements mapping matrix are also updated regularly, so any missing requirement or new risk is captured quickly. Overall, ArgonDigital's frequent status meetings and dashboards enact ISO's monitoring step by constantly re-evaluating risk status against business objectives.

2.3.6 Recording and Reporting

The Recording and Reporting stage is not just a final administrative step — it's the cornerstone of maintaining accountability, auditability, and learning in risk-driven requirements engineering. Without

it, the rationale behind many system requirements may be lost, misunderstood, or ignored. This stage addresses some important issues of risk and requirements integration:

- Ensuring that all risk-based requirements can be tracked for review and audit.
- Documenting the rationale for critical and high value requirements.
- Informing stakeholders of how requirements impact risks.
- Demonstrating that risk-related requirements meet legal or policy mandates.
- Supporting the reuse of effective risk management requirements in other projects.

KAOS

KAOS inherently records rationale. The final goal–obstacle–agent models, with all refinements, serve as documentation of the risk decisions. For example, every obstacle and its resolution path is captured in the model. KAOS tools (like Objectiver or OpenOME) can export these models and show traceability matrices between goals, requirements, and obstacles. Thus one can generate reports such as “which requirements implement security goals that guard against obstacle X.” In ISO terms, the entire KAOS modeling artifact is the “record” – it contains context, assessment, and treatment information. When asked for a risk report, the team can present the goal graph annotated with metrics or the domain model highlighting assumptions. In short, KAOS records are structured and formal, aligning well with ISO 31000’s emphasis on documentation: nothing is informal or lost because the model itself is a living database.

i*

In i*, the final SD/SR models are the prime records. If risk analysis was performed, one can annotate the i* model (or attach a separate risk register table) with the identified risks and chosen mitigations. Tools like OpenOME allow exporting the model to XMI or PDF, which can be delivered to stakeholders as documentation. The i* models inherently show which goals depend on which, so one can trace a requirement back to the goal whose failure it mitigates. As a reporting artifact, one might include diagrams (e.g. annotated goal graphs) in a requirements spec. While i* doesn’t enforce a format for risk reports, teams typically produce a risk matrix or list alongside the model. Thus the combination of the i* diagrams plus any risk logs constitutes the report. In practice, i*’s captured rationale (as goals and dependencies) is used to explain the risk-related design choices to reviewers, satisfying ISO’s need for transparent recording of risk management outcomes.

ArgonDigital

ArgonDigital’s approach ensures traceability and reporting by design. A requirements mapping matrix connects every requirement to its originating feature and objective [7]. This matrix is the key record: it shows exactly why a requirement exists (which objective it supports). In addition, the visual models (objectives, process steps, data) form the backdrop for requirements derivation. Together, these artifacts document the “why” of each requirement. Reporting is done through stakeholder communications: the weekly status report (with risk section) and issue logs are formally shared documents that capture risk events and resolutions. For instance, the weekly report lists any risks identified and how they were addressed. By keeping all requirements and issues in tracking tools (and linking them to features/objectives), ArgonDigital produces an audit trail of decisions, which fulfills ISO’s “recording and reporting” step. The team can print out the mapping matrix or status reports as proof of risk management activity.

2.4 Summary of Gaps in Existing Work

Although multiple methods attempt to relate risk to requirements, most fail to offer an integrated, executable, and standards-aligned architecture.

KAOS

KAOS supports structured approach to goal modeling and decomposition. It provides good identifying risks related to missing or conflicting goals and partial risk analysis via obstacles and countermeasures. However, KAOS lacks support for the full ISO 31000 lifecycle and broader organizational integration. It is not designed for risk evaluation, treatment, monitoring, or organizational integration, and it does not natively support stakeholder engagement, dynamic feedback, or cultural context.

i*

Although i* is strong in early-stage risk identification (from unmet goals or failed dependencies), particularly socio-technical dependencies, and can help analyze stakeholder concerns and detect vulnerabilities in intentions or commitments, it lacks the full risk management cycle and organizational adaptability required by ISO 31000, namely:

- No native support for risk treatment, monitoring, or feedback loops.
- Limited support for integration into broader management processes.
- No emphasis on human factors, continual improvement, or communication plans.

ArgonDigital

ArgonDigital aligns closely with ISO 31000’s recommendations, focusing on requirements risk identification, tracking, and treatment, but does not fully address cultural, adaptive, or broader enterprise contexts. In particular, it lacks:

- Formality for iterative monitoring or continuous improvement.
- Systematic exposure to cultural/human factors.
- Generalized support for non-compliance risks.

This analysis motivates the development of an ontologically grounded architecture that integrates risk models into the requirements framework while supporting formal reasoning, automation, and alignment with ISO standards. Table 5 summarizes the main limitations of existing approaches compared to the proposed framework.

Table 5: Comparison of Selected Risk-Requirements Integration Approaches

Approach	ISO 31000 Alignment	Executable	RM Cycle Support
KAOS+Obstacles	Partial	No	Partial
i* with Risks	Partial	No	Partial
ArgonDigital	Strong	No	Near-Full
Proposed Framework	Strong	Yes	Full

3 Proposed Framework

3.1 Ontology Construction Approach

The early stages of software development—particularly requirements engineering—play a critical role in determining project success. Numerous studies and industry reports cite poorly defined or misunderstood requirements as a major contributor to project failure, delays, or cost overruns. While risk management is widely acknowledged as essential in software engineering, its systematic integration into the requirements engineering process remains fragmented and often ad hoc.

Existing goal-oriented modeling approaches such as KAOS and i* offer partial support for capturing and reasoning about risks: KAOS through obstacles and anti-goals, and i* through modeling of vulnerable actor dependencies. However, these methods are either too formal for broad industrial adoption or lack executable semantics for operational deployment. On the other hand, practitioner-driven frameworks such as ArgonDigital focus on reducing risk through improved requirements communication and visualization, yet do not provide a formal risk management structure aligned with goal models or ontology-based reasoning.

Thus, current techniques often fail to provide:

- a unified, goal-driven approach to modeling both requirements and risks;
- formal semantics to enable automated validation, traceability, and inference;
- alignment between stakeholder objectives and risk-aware system behaviors;
- executable artifacts capable of supporting dynamic adaptation or runtime assurance.

These limitations motivate the development of a novel framework that integrates risk management into the architecture of requirements using executable ontology. By leveraging semantic networks, goal decomposition, and transcendental logic for reasoning about risk-laden dependencies and constraints, the proposed approach aims to bridge the gap between conceptual models and practical implementation. The ultimate objective is to enable both human analysts and intelligent agents to operate on a shared, formalized, and evolvable knowledge base that governs requirements under uncertainty.

To make the integration of risks and requirements not only systematic, but also automated, you need to formalize knowledge and relationships between objects and an executable ontological approach. Thus, an executable ontology is exactly the tool that paves the way for an automated context-oriented model of the relationship between requirements and risks. An executable ontology (i.e., a formal knowledge model) not only describes concepts and relationships, but also:

- has a formal logic (e.g., OWL and SWRL rules),
- can be executed on reasoning engines (such as Pellet, HermiT),
- supports querying, inference, validation, and simulation of knowledge.

In other words, it is not just a “knowledge base” but an active system (framework) that can, for example:

- tell which requirements fall under the “Integration Interface Mismatch” risk class;
- check whether the risks are correctly associated with the categories of requirements;
- automatically generate mitigation recommendations based on ontological relationships.

In this section, we’ll show how you can build a framework for integrating risk models, requirements models, and project artifacts in the form of an executable ontology. Unlike formal methods such as KAOS or actor-centric models like i*, our proposed framework begins with a pragmatic artifact structure inspired by ArgonDigital. This foundation is then ontologically enriched and made executable through a transcendental logic layer that defines dynamic interrelations among requirements elements. Thus, the advantages of this approach to ontological modeling of the integrated requirements architecture are as follows:

1. Classical frameworks such as KAOS and i* already have well-established formalisms, axiomatics, and semantics. Being based on formal and semi-formal logic, they are limited in their ability to express non-traditional logical relations such as apodictic/hypothetical, antinomian, or quasi-causal structures, unlike transcendental logic.
2. The semantics of an executable ontology allows not only declarative modeling, but also behavioral scenarios, reactive logics, and self-correction, i.e., dynamic properties.

3. The artifact-oriented ArgonDigital framework can be easily extended or transformed into an ontological (formal) form. In doing so, you can create your own semantics not only for models of functional/non-functional requirements, but also for business rules, test cases, scenarios, model elements such as process or value flow steps, or for any project artifact that requires special attention.

The proposed ontology is intended to serve as a semantic backbone for integrating goal-oriented requirements models with risk management processes. Unlike traditional frameworks such as KAOS or i^* , our approach does not rely on predefined formal logics or fixed modeling grammars. Instead, it adopts a lightweight ontological foundation grounded in transcendental logic, where relationships between concepts are defined not only structurally, but also in terms of their epistemic and operational roles within a requirements architecture.

3.1.1 Modeling Foundations

Our ontology is developed from scratch and aligns closely with the visual modeling primitives of ArgonDigital’s Requirements Modeling Language (RML), such as Business Objectives Models, Objective Chains, Feature Trees, and Requirements Mapping Matrices. These models provide an intuitive and industry-proven conceptual structure that we use to derive core ontological classes (e.g., `Risk`, `Goal`, `Feature`, `Requirement`, `Metric`, `StakeholderIntent`).

Each model type in RML is mapped to a distinct meta-class within the ontology. Relationships such as “supports,” “conflicts with,” or “refines” are treated as first-class semantic properties, allowing for rule-based reasoning about the consistency, feasibility, and traceability of requirements.

3.1.2 Transcendental Logic of Relations

Instead of relying on temporal or modal logic (as in KAOS) or social dependency logic (as in i^*), our framework introduces a transcendental logic of relations between requirements artifacts according to Kantian “ontological predicates” [23]. These predicates introduce the ontological relations derived from the well-known categories of Kant’s reason, and their peculiarity is that they do not show the properties of the objects they refer to, but indicate how we should, guided by them, reveal the properties and relations of the objects of experience in general. As Kant noted, they have a “regulative application” in relation to the properties and relationships of objects that are manifested in reality [22]. In essence, we are talking about an alternative way of developing symbolic computing based on transcendental logic by introducing universal ontological relations between semantically close concepts. These relations are as follows:

1. Relation of subordination (genus-specie).
2. Relation of generality (general-individual).
3. Relation of aggregation (part-integer),
4. Relation of modality (conditionally-unconditionally, possibly-impossibly, necessarily-optionally, existence-nonexistence etc.)
5. Relation of order (more-less, higher-lower, etc.),
6. Relation of causality (cause-effect),
7. Relation of tactility (degree of semantic proximity)
8. Relation of vitality (role in the life of the individual)
9. Relation of wisdom (influence on mental abilities or reasoning in a broad sense)
10. Relation of chaos (randomness of the established relationship)
11. Relation of variability (the ability to change categories themselves)
12. Relation of effectiveness (ability to generate control instructions)

These ontological predicates form an abstract semantic framework on which ontology can be built in each specific domain. In the software requirements engineering, they allow you to have a clear unambiguous understanding of the nature of the relationships between requirements. This is important because models can influence each other in different ways. For example, some models are based on others if there are causal relationships between them, or models can provide information for other models if there is a certain sequence of actions in the process flow, or one model is linked to another model, which in turn is linked to once more model (cascading relationships).

The examples below show some of the most commonly used relationships between requirements, risks and artifacts in ontologies, as well as the ontological predicates that govern these relationships:

- Artifact *satisfies* Requirement → Relation of causality
- Artifact *isDerivedFrom* Requirement → Relation of causality
- Requirement *affectsByRisk* Requirement → Relation of variability
- Requirement *refines* Requirement → Relation of variability
- Requirement *createdBy* Business Goal → Relation of wisdom
- Requirement *hasRelatedStakeholder* Stakeholder → Relation of tactility

3.1.3 Risk Model Integration

To integrate risk management, we extend the ontology with classes such as `RiskFactor`, `Hazard`, `MitigationStrategy`, and `ThreatScenario`, and define their interactions with goals, features, peoples, systems, and data. Rather than being treated as external annotations, risk elements are considered ontologically embedded concepts that shape the system's structure and behavior through reifying relationships.

Relationships between objects, especially if they are not binary, are the most problematic place in building ontology, especially in ontology learning. Basic semantics lives in relationships, but why are relationships always difficult? There are several reasons:

1. Relationships are not always binary, for example, "Risk affects the requirement in a certain scenario" is a ternary relationship.
2. Relationships can be contextual - the same relationship can have different consequences depending on the project phase or role.
3. Relationships usually require attributes - relationships themselves often have properties (e.g., "probability", "criticality").

The relational model responds to this by creating additional tables. The ontology model, on the other hand, reifies relationships, i.e. it turns an-ary relationships into an object. So, in the case of the Goal → Requirement → Risk ontology, instead of creating many relationships between each individual element, we create a single object of type `RiskObject` or `RiskEvent` that contains links to all related elements as attributes. For example:

```
### System objects
:Goal_G1 a :Goal ;
    rdfs:label "Ensure customer data integrity" .

:Requirement_R1 a :Requirement ;
    rdfs:label "Encrypt customer records at rest" .

:System_S1 a :System ;
    rdfs:label "Data Storage Module" .

:DataModel_D1 a :DataModel ;
    rdfs:label "CustomerRecord" .
```

```

:Hazard_H1 a :Hazard ;
  rdfs:label "Unauthorized access to raw storage" .

:Strategy_M1 a :MitigationStrategy ;
  rdfs:label "Implement AES-256 encryption with access logs" .

### Risk objects
:Risk-R123 a :RiskObject ;
  rdfs:label "Storage encryption failure risk" ;
  :affectsGoal :Goal_G1 ;
  :affectsRequirement :Requirement_R1 ;
  :affectsSystem :System_S1 ;
  :involvesData :DataModel_D1 ;
  :hasHazard :Hazard_H1 ;
  :hasMitigationStrategy :Strategy_M1 ;
  :likelihood "0.4"^^xsd:decimal ;
  :severity "High" .

```

In this example, a single risk object `Risk-R123` is created that refers to:

- the goal it affects ,
- the implementation system,
- the requirement to be tested,
- the associated hazard scenario,
- the associated mitigation plan.

Thus, this approach centralizes risk knowledge, enabling it to be analyzed, filtered and compared. It also simplifies reasoning, as every relationship can be deduced or verified. It is semantically coherent because risk 'lives' as a separate concept, and it is scalable because it allows you to work with lots of risks.

3.1.4 Execution Semantics and Future Work

Although the ontology is initially specified in a descriptive logic-compatible form (e.g., OWL 2), we aim to enrich it with executable semantics via rule-based systems (e.g., SWRL or SPARQL rules). These will allow reasoning over requirement satisfaction, conflict detection, and dynamic risk propagation.

The development process follows an iterative, layered methodology: starting from conceptual model extraction, through ontological abstraction, to executable formalization. This approach supports modularity, extensibility, and traceability — key criteria for practical adoption in real-world requirements engineering.

Executable requirement models, especially those formalized as ontology, can support continuous validation of system behavior against evolving risks. This is critical in dynamic or adaptive systems, where risks and requirements co-evolve.

3.2 Ontology Meta-Architecture

The proposed meta-architecture defines a super-ontology that unifies two complementary sub-ontologies: a goal-driven requirements sub-ontology and an ISO-based risk sub-ontology. In the requirements sub-ontology, each high-level model is treated as an ontological class (*BusinessObjective*, *People*, *System*, and *Data*). This structure follows ArgonDigital's methodology, where features are explicitly linked to business objectives (goals) and requirements are in turn traced to features. For instance, ArgonDigital notes that "every requirement will eventually be traced back to a feature, and every feature must be traced directly to a business objective" [7]. In the risk sub-ontology, classes include standard ISO artifacts such as *Risk Register*, *Risk Assessment Matrix*, or *Mitigation Plan* (risk treatment strategies). The super-ontology declares these classes at the top level and ensures that each model (e.g. one particular feature model or risk matrix) is represented by an instance of the corresponding class.

3.2.1 Layered Hierarchy of Models

The integrated ontology is organized in a layered hierarchy reflecting dependencies between model categories. At the top are goal (objective) models, which capture high-level stakeholder or business objectives. These goal models govern the next layer of People and System models (e.g. user roles, organizational units, system components) because achieving a goal requires certain human or system actors to be involved. In turn, People and System models influence the Data models (information and data elements used or produced by the system). This layered perspective parallels ArgonDigital’s visual modeling in four categories (Objectives, People, Systems, Data). In practice, one can say that a high-level Objective/Goal defines or requires specific System or People elements, which in turn define certain Data requirements. For example, a “Customer Support” goal might determine a set of user roles (People) and modules (Systems) that handle support cases, and those modules will then produce or consume specific Data (e.g., customer records, ticket logs).

Crucially, risk models span these layers by representing potential disruptions or dependencies across goals and system elements. Risk classes link goals with each other (capturing goal-to-goal dependencies or conflicts) and with People/System models (identifying risks that affect actors or components). In other words, a risk event might trigger a deviation in a goal’s fulfillment or require additional controls in a system. For instance, two goals may have a contradicts relation if pursuing one inherently increases risk to the other. This means risk ontology classes (e.g. a specific Risk instance) can point to one Goal and a relevant System or Person as context. Overall, risk models provide cross-cutting connectors in the ontology, linking the goal layer with operational layers to encode how failures or threats propagate through the structure.

3.2.2 Semantic Predicates and Inter-Model Relations

Relationships between the ontological classes are expressed via a rich set of high-level ontological predicates mentioned above. As noted, these predicates serve as universal relation types that capture the meaning of links between model concepts. For example, *ObjectiveChain* class define a *Feature* class to be implemented, because corresponding requirements models are related by the predicate ”Relation of causality”. Similarly, ontological predicates can be used to encode semantic links between any requirements and artifacts, enabling an executable semantic framework.

In the meta-architecture, each predicate instantiation is a cross-model link that can be “executed” in the sense of driving reasoning. For example, if a link is triggered from a *RiskEvent* class to a *Requirement* class, it means that if the risk materialises, the status of the requirement must be re-assessed. In summary, the ontology defines these relations abstractly to form a network of constraints and dependencies. This lets one formally capture, for instance, that a Risk requires updating a Goal, or that a Data model concept subsumes another, etc.

3.2.3 Risk Object Instantiation

The final aspect of the meta-architecture is that specific risk instances (risk objects) can be created to tie particular goals to concrete risk models. A risk object connects a specific Goal node with a particular ISO-based risk artifact, and optionally to any relevant People, System, or Data instances. Conceptually, this means instantiating, say, a *RiskEvent* that links Goal “G” with *RiskRegister* entry “R” and with *System* “S” if that system is implicated. This risk object represents a concrete vulnerability or threat scenario. In practice, one would use such objects to record that a certain goal has a certain risk score (from the risk matrix) and a designated mitigation plan. Because all risk artifacts are classes in the ontology, these object instances enable automated reasoning: for example, if a risk object triggers a system failure, the ontology can infer which requirements (linked to that system and goal) are affected. This completes the meta-architecture: a layered, semantically rich ontology where goal-driven requirements and ISO-compliant risk concepts coexist and interoperate.

3.3 Ontology Formalization

The sketch of the executable ontology that underlies the proposed framework can be found in Appendix A. It has been formalized using RDF/OWL and enriched with a layer of reified universal predicates. The structure consists of two primary extensions:

- **Domain Ontology Layer**, which defines core domain concepts such as `Goal`, `Requirement`, `System`, `Person`, and ISO-compliant risk management artifacts including `RiskObject`, `RiskRegister`, and `MitigationStrategy`.
- **Meta-Semantic Layer**, built around a generic `Predicate` class and a reified `SemanticLink`, enabling n-ary relations that explicitly encode semantic intent (e.g., `Causality`, `Aggregation`, `Modality`).

Risk elements are represented as individuals of class `RiskObject`, with properties linking them to impacted elements such as `Goal`, `Requirement`, `System`, `Person`, and `Data`. Semantic relations are reified using `SemanticLink` instances, which associate a subject and object through an ontological predicate, allowing for advanced semantic reasoning.

To support rule-based classification, the ontology includes datatype properties such as `likelihood` and `severity`. These enable the execution of SWRL rules such as, for example, "If a risk has a severity of `High` and a likelihood above 0.5, it is classified as a `CriticalRisk`". The corresponding SWRL implementation of the rule is:

```
RiskObject(?r) ^ severity(?r, "High") ^ likelihood(?r, ?p) ^
swrlb:greaterThan(?p, 0.5)
-> CriticalRisk(?r)
```

Similarly, we can implement SWRL rules to identify, for example, interrelated risks:

1. Identify risks that are linked by a causal relationship:

```
SemanticLink(?link) ^ hasSubject(?link, ?r1) ^ hasObject(?link, ?r2) ^
hasPredicate(?link, pred:Causality) ^ RiskObject(?r1) ^ RiskObject(?r2)
→
RelatedRiskPair(?r1, ?r2)
```

2. Identify risks that mutually reinforce each other:

```
SemanticLink(?link1) ^ hasSubject(?link1, ?r1) ^ hasObject(?link1, ?r2) ^
SemanticLink(?link2) ^ hasSubject(?link2, ?r2) ^ hasObject(?link2, ?r1) ^
hasPredicate(?link1, pred:Vitality) ^ hasPredicate(?link2, pred:Vitality) ^
RiskObject(?r1) ^ RiskObject(?r2)
→
MutuallyReinforcedRisks(?r1, ?r2)
```

3. Identify risks that affect the same target

```
RiskObject(?r1) ^ impactsGoal(?r1, ?g) ^ RiskObject(?r2) ^
impactsGoal(?r2, ?g) ^ swrlb:notEqual(?r1, ?r2)
→
GoalLinkedRisks(?r1, ?r2)
```

4. Identify critical risks that are interrelated:

```
RiskObject(?r1) ^ RiskObject(?r2) ^ severity(?r1, "High") ^
severity(?r2, "High") ^ likelihood(?r1, ?p1) ^ likelihood(?r2, ?p2) ^
swrlb:greaterThan(?p1, 0.5) ^ swrlb:greaterThan(?p2, 0.5) ^ SemanticLink(?link) ^
hasSubject(?link, ?r1) ^ hasObject(?link, ?r2)
→
CriticalInteractingRisks(?r1, ?r2)
```

4 Evaluation and Discussion

This section provides an analytical comparison between the proposed ontology-based framework and the well-established KAOS methodology. The discussion is structured along three key dimensions: formalism, limitations, and conceptual contributions. Through this comparison, we aim to clarify the benefits and trade-offs introduced by our executable ontology approach in the context of risk-aware requirements engineering.

4.1 Formalism Comparison

The executable ontology replaces hierarchical refinements with flexible reified relationships among elements such as goals, systems, and risk entities. By treating relations as first-class ontological objects, the framework enables dynamic inference and advanced querying beyond static obstacle trees.

The Table 6 shows the main elements of the formalism of the proposed framework in comparison with the KAOS formalism.

Table 6: Formalism comparison: KAOS vs. Proposed Framework.

Aspect	KAOS	Proposed Framework
Logic foundation	Temporal logic (LTL) + FOL	OWL DL + SWRL + reified RDF model
Modeling style	Goal trees, obstacles	Ontological graph with reified n-ary links
Risk representation	Obstacles and anti-goals	Explicit <code>RiskObject</code> class with typed relations
Traceability	Goal decomposition with refinement links	Semantic graph with universal predicates
Execution support	Limited to verification logic	SWRL-based rule execution, SPARQL reasoning

4.2 Limitations Analysis

Although KAOS benefits from its tight formalism, it lacks extensibility and direct support for dynamic risk models. The ontology-based framework offers greater flexibility but requires disciplined ontology engineering practices for scalability and coherence.

The Table 7 shows the results of the limitations comparison of the proposed framework and KAOS.

Table 7: Limitations comparison: KAOS vs. Proposed Framework.

Limitation	KAOS	Proposed Framework
Tool dependency	Dedicated (Objectiver)	Generic OWL tools (Protégé, Jena, etc.)
Learning curve	Steep (formal logic, decomposition)	Moderate (ontology modeling + SWRL)
Goal abstraction	Strong built-in structure	External structuring (e.g., ArgonDigital hierarchy)
Risk model scope	Focused on goal negation	Integrates full ISO-based risk models
Stakeholder visibility	Abstract logic-based	Graph-based, queryable and extensible

4.3 Conceptual Extensions and Implications

The proposed framework introduces three significant conceptual advancements over KAOS:

1. **Ontological Reification of Semantic Relations** — all semantic links are instantiated via `SemanticLink` objects governed by a reusable predicate ontology (e.g., `Causality`, `Subordination`, `Modality`). This allows for flexible, interpretable, and analyzable model interconnections.
2. **Risk-Requirement Integration as Executable Knowledge** — rather than treating risks as obstacles, the framework represents risks as structured individuals linked to multiple system elements and enriched with metadata (likelihood, severity, mitigation strategy).
3. **Layered Architecture with Semantic Propagation** — risks can propagate across goal, system, and data layers via defined predicates, enabling simulations of cascading failures or mitigation planning through reasoning.

Thus, this framework promotes a shift from document-based or tree-based models to semantically grounded, executable knowledge graphs. It enables:

- Automated impact analysis across requirements layers.
- Integration with risk registries, rule engines, and intelligent agents.
- Reuse of formalized patterns across domains and project contexts.

Overall, the framework supports a more adaptive, explainable and auditable requirements engineering process by embedding risks and requirements into a unified ontological structure.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

This paper proposed a formal framework for integrating risk management into requirements engineering through an executable ontology. The ontology is structured around reified semantic links and a set of universal ontological predicates, enabling rich and scalable semantic modeling of relationships between business goals, requirements, system components, data artifacts, and ISO-standard risk elements.

The proposed approach offers several key benefits:

- A unified semantic model that embeds risk concepts as ontological individuals connected to goals, requirements, systems, and data.
- Use of reified n-ary relations to capture complex dependencies, facilitating cross-domain reasoning and interpretability.
- Executability through SWRL rules and SPARQL queries, supporting inference, conflict detection, and traceability.

Compared to traditional formalisms such as KAOS, the framework shifts from obstacle modeling toward a modular, queryable, and semantically expressive structure. Risks are not limited to logical negations but treated as dynamically instantiated, assessable, and traceable entities with semantic properties and structural impact.

Future work will focus on two main directions:

1. **Ontology Learning and Automation:** Methods for semi-automated extraction of ontology instances and semantic links from visual models, specifications, or logs using NLP and knowledge graph embedding techniques.
2. **Executable Transformation Pipelines:** Creating bidirectional mappings between the ontology and external engineering artifacts (e.g., risk registers, BPMN models, or requirements tools), enabling simulation, synchronization, and automated audits.

Ultimately, the framework lays a foundation for a new class of intelligent, explainable, and adaptive tools in requirements-centric systems engineering, where universal semantic relationships and risk-awareness are embedded from the ground up.

A Appendix A: RDF/OWL Ontology Core

Below is a fragment of the RDF/OWL ontology definition, expressed in Turtle syntax, annotated with inline comments:

```
### Core requirement and risk classes
:Goal          a owl:Class .
:Requirement    a owl:Class .
:System        a owl:Class .
:Person        a owl:Class .
>Data          a owl:Class .
:RiskObject    a owl:Class .
:MitigationStrategy a owl:Class .

### Universal predicate framework
pred:Predicate  a owl:Class . # Base class for ontological relations
pred:SemanticLink a owl:Class . # Reified relation: subject, predicate, object

pred:hasSubject  a owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:domain pred:SemanticLink ;
  rdfs:range  owl:Thing .

pred:hasObject   a owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:domain pred:SemanticLink ;
  rdfs:range  owl:Thing .

pred:hasPredicate a owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:domain pred:SemanticLink ;
  rdfs:range  pred:Predicate .

### Predicate classes
pred:Causality   a owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf pred:Predicate ;
  rdfs:label "Causality" ;
  rdfs:comment "Relation of causality" .

pred:Aggregation a owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf pred:Predicate ;
  rdfs:label "Aggregation" ;
  rdfs:comment "Relation of aggregation" .

pred:Subordination a owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf pred:Predicate ;
  rdfs:label "Subordination" ;
  rdfs:comment "Relation of subordination" .

pred:Generality  a owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf pred:Predicate ;
  rdfs:label "Generality" ;
  rdfs:comment "Relation of generality" .

pred:Modality    a owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf pred:Predicate ;
  rdfs:label "Modality" ;
  rdfs:comment "Relation of modality" .

pred:Order       a owl:Class ;
```

```

    rdfs:subClassOf pred:Predicate ;
    rdfs:label "Order" ;
    rdfs:comment "Relation of order" .

pred:Tactility      a owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf pred:Predicate ;
    rdfs:label "Tactility" ;
    rdfs:comment "Relation of tactility" .

pred:Vitality       a owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf pred:Predicate ;
    rdfs:label "Vitality" ;
    rdfs:comment "Relation of vitality" .

pred:Wisdom         a owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf pred:Predicate ;
    rdfs:label "Wisdom" ;
    rdfs:comment "Relation of wisdom" .

pred:Chaos          a owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf pred:Predicate ;
    rdfs:label "Chaos" ;
    rdfs:comment "Relation of chaos" .

pred:Variability    a owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf pred:Predicate ;
    rdfs:label "Variability" ;
    rdfs:comment "Relation of variability" .

pred:Effectiveness  a owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf pred:Predicate ;
    rdfs:label "Effectiveness" ;
    rdfs:comment "Relation of effectiveness" .

### Linking risks to requirements and goals
:hasAssociatedRisk  a owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:domain :Requirement ;
    rdfs:range  :RiskObject .

:impactsGoal       a owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:domain :RiskObject ;
    rdfs:range  :Goal .

:requiresMitigation a owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:domain :RiskObject ;
    rdfs:range  :MitigationStrategy .

### Risk properties for reasoning
:likelihood        a owl:DatatypeProperty ;
    rdfs:domain :RiskObject ;
    rdfs:range  xsd:decimal .

:severity          a owl:DatatypeProperty ;
    rdfs:domain :RiskObject ;
    rdfs:range  xsd:string .

```

```

### Classification class
:CriticalRisk      a owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :RiskObject .

### Inferred risk interaction patterns (for SWRL reasoning)
:DerivedRiskPatterns a owl:Class ;
    rdfs:label "Derived Risk Patterns" ;
    rdfs:comment "A superclass for inferred risk interaction classes generated via SWRL or other reasons" .

:RelatedRiskPair   a owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :DerivedRiskPatterns .

:MutuallyReinforcedRisks a owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :DerivedRiskPatterns .

:GoalLinkedRisks    a owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :DerivedRiskPatterns .

:CriticalInteractingRisks a owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :DerivedRiskPatterns .

```

References

- [1] H. Alaidaros, A. Bakodah, and S. F. Bamsaoud. A review on requirements prioritization approaches of software project management. In *2022 International Technical Symposium on Information Technology and Smart Systems (ITSS-IoE)*, pages 25–30, 2022.
- [2] ArgonDigital. Business objectives model. <https://argondigital.com/resource/tools-templates/business-objective-models/>, 2024. Accessed June 4, 2025.
- [3] ArgonDigital. Feature trees. <https://argondigital.com/resource/tools-templates/rml-objectives-models/feature-trees/>, 2024. Accessed June 4, 2025.
- [4] ArgonDigital. Key performance indicator (kpi) models. <https://argondigital.com/resource/tools-templates/rml-objectives-models/key-performance-indicator-models/>, 2024. Accessed June 4, 2025.
- [5] ArgonDigital. Objective chains. <https://argondigital.com/resource/tools-templates/objective-chains-2/>, 2024. Accessed June 4, 2025.
- [6] ArgonDigital. Requirements mapping matrices. <https://argondigital.com/resource/tools-templates/rml-objectives-models/requirements-mapping-matrices/>, 2024. Accessed June 4, 2025.
- [7] ArgonDigital (formerly Seilevel). ArgonDigital Requirements Methodology: Integrating Visual Models. <https://argondigital.com/resource/whitepapers/argondigital-requirements-methodology/>, n.d. Accessed: 2025-06-14.
- [8] Henri Barki, Suzanne Rivard, and Jean Talbot and. An integrative contingency model of software project risk management. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 17(4):37–69, 2001.
- [9] Joy Beatty and Anthony Chen. *Visual Models for Software Requirements*. Microsoft Press, 2015. Practical guide based on ArgonDigital (formerly Seilevel) methodology.
- [10] K. Boness, A. Finkelstein, and R. Harrison. A lightweight technique for assessing risks in requirements analysis. *IET Software*, 2(1):32–41, 2008.
- [11] R. S. Dewi. Reclassify and readjust software risk taxonomy in software development activities context. In *2022 International Conference on Information and Communications Technology (ICOIACT)*, pages 589–594, 2022.

- [12] Brian P. Gallagher, James McMahon, and Carol Woody. A taxonomy of operational risks. Technical Report CMU/SEI-2005-TN-036, Software Engineering Institute, Carnegie Mellon University, 2005. Technical Note, September 2005.
- [13] Constantinos Giannoulis and Jelena Zdravković. Exploring risk-awareness in i* models. In *Proceedings of the 10th International i* Workshop*, volume 586 of *CEUR Workshop Proceedings*, pages 1032–1045, Kaiserslautern, Germany, 2010. CEUR-WS.org.
- [14] Mark Harman and Francisco Chicano. Search based software engineering (sbse). *Journal of Systems and Software*, 117:152–173, 2015.
- [15] International Organization for Standardization. Iso 31000:2018 — risk management – guidelines. <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:31000:ed-2:v1:en>, 2018. Accessed: 2025-06-04.
- [16] International Organization for Standardization. ISO/IEC 31010:2019 — Risk management — Risk assessment techniques. <https://www.iso.org/standard/73367.html>, 2019. International Standard, ISO/IEC.
- [17] Shareeful Islam. *Software Development Risk Management Model: A Goal-Driven Approach*. Ph.d. dissertation, Technische Universität Darmstadt, 2011.
- [18] Richard Knaster and Dean Leffingwell. *SAFe 5.0 Distilled: Achieving Business Agility with the Scaled Agile Framework*. Addison-Wesley Professional, 2019.
- [19] B. K. Lyon and G. Popov. The art of assessing risk. *Professional Safety*, 61(3):40–51, March 2016. Accessed via ASSP website.
- [20] Jhon Masso, José Luis Fernández-Alemán, and Ambrosio Toval. Risk management in the software life cycle: A systematic literature review. *Computer Standards & Interfaces*, 69:103431, 2020.
- [21] Julio Menezes et al. Risk factors in software development projects: a systematic literature review. *Software Quality Journal*, 27(1):1–57, 2019.
- [22] Oleg V. Moroz. Universal transcendental logic-based ontology. *Computer and Information Science*, 14(2):1–16, 2021.
- [23] Oleg V. Moroz, Oleksii O. Pysarchuk, and Tetiana I. Konrad. Transcendental logic-based formalism for semantic representation of software project requirements architecture. *Computer and Information Science*, 15(2):15–28, 2022. Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License.
- [24] NASA. Nasa risk management handbook. Technical Report NASA/SP-2011-3422, NASA Headquarters, Washington, DC, 2011. Definition of risk model: A structured (qualitative or quantitative) representation that integrates uncertainty sources and their impacts to inform decision-making.
- [25] Project Management Institute. *A Guide to the Project Management Body of Knowledge (PMBOK Guide)*. Project Management Institute, Newtown Square, PA, 6th edition, 2017. Definition of risk model: A representation of how uncertainty elements (events, probabilities, impacts, mitigations) interact to affect project objectives.
- [26] Aurora Ramírez, Juan J. Durillo, and Enrique Alba. A survey of many-objective optimisation in search-based software engineering. *Journal of Systems and Software*, 149:382–399, 2019.
- [27] P. Thanomwong and T. Senivongse. User story risk prioritization model for agile software development. In *2022 International Conference on Data and Software Engineering (ICoDSE)*, pages 79–84, 2022.
- [28] Axel van Lamsweerde. *Requirements Engineering: From System Goals to UML Models to Software Specifications*. Wiley, 2009. Main reference for the KAOS methodology.
- [29] Linda Wallace, Mark Keil, and Arun Rai. How software project risk affects project performance: An investigation of the dimensions of risk and an exploratory model. *Decision Sciences*, 35(2):289–321, 2004.

- [30] Lou Wheatcraft. Requirement metrics on the stability and risks of requirements. Blog post, 2013. Accessed June 2025.
- [31] Eric S. K. Yu. Towards modeling and reasoning support for early-phase requirements engineering. In *Proceedings of the 3rd IEEE International Symposium on Requirements Engineering (RE '97)*, pages 226–235. IEEE, 1997. Seminal paper on the i* framework.